

Thiodiazines. Part V.

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It has been shown by one of us (Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 50; *ibid.*, 1925, 2, 25) that thiosemicarbazide and 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides readily condense with ω -bromacetophenone to give rise to 1:3:4-thiodiazine derivatives, the system taking part being $-C(SH):N.NH$ and $BrCH_2CO-$. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to examine if 2:4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides, $RNH.CS.N(R')NH_2$, or $RN=C(SH).NR'.NH_2$, which contain the necessary reactive groups for the thiodiazine-ring formation would also condense in a similar way with halogenated ketones to yield thiodiazines of the type (I) thus:

This expectation has been amply realised. In the present investigation we have employed monochloracetone, ω -bromacetophenone and *p*-methyl- ω -bromacetophenone on the one hand and 2:4-diphenyl, 2-phenyl-4-*p*-tolyl, 2-phenyl-4-*o*-tolyl, 2-phenyl-4-*m*-tolyl, 2-*p*-tolyl-4-phenyl, 2-*p*-tolyl-4-*o*-tolyl, 2:4-di-*p*-tolyl, 2-*p*-tolyl-4-*o*-anisyl, 2-*p*-tolyl-4-*m*-tolyl, and 2-*m*-tolyl-4-phenyl-thiosemicarbazides on the other; of these 2-phenyl-4-*m*-tolyl, 2-*p*-tolyl-4-*o*-anisyl, and 2-*p*-tolyl-4-*m*-tolyl thiosemicarbazides appear to be new.

The reaction in all cases can be brought about by heating for a short time equimolecular quantities of the reactants in dry alcohol. Alcohol may also be replaced by acetic acid or pyridine. The use of the last solvent as a medium in the above condensation is rather restricted as some of 2:4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides easily undergo conversion into the 1:4-variety in this solvent, the halogenated ketone at the same time reacts with pyridine or with 1:4-compounds to give uncrystallisable products. If however the 2:4-compound be not very susceptible to the 1:4-transformation in this solvent, the halogenated ketone reacts chiefly with the thiosemicarbazide.

The thiodiazines thus obtained are stable crystalline substances most of which are colourless. They are rather weak bases since the hydrochlorides or hydrobromides readily hydrolyse in aqueous solution and if sufficient water be present, the base is precipitated. They are not desulphurised when boiled with freshly precipitated mercuric oxide or with alkaline lead acetate solution.

Attempts to acetylate these compounds by means of acetic anhydride or acetyl chloride in pyridine solution were fruitless. The thiodiazines also failed to react with phenyl mustard oil when heated in acetone solution for 8 hours. It is difficult at this stage to state definitely whether the non-reactivity of the imino hydrogen atom is to be attributed to steric influence of the adjoining radicles on either side of the NH group in position 4 or to the alternate configuration (II).

1:4-Diphenyl-thiosemicarbazide reacts with ω -bromacetophenone in boiling alcoholic solution but from the resulting tarry product the expected thiodiazine (III) could not be isolated.

(III)

If however equivalent quantities of the reactants are suspended in alcohol and left at the room temperature for several months, condensation takes place very slowly, and the resulting product is found to be identical with that derived from 2:4-diphenyl thiosemicarbazide, namely 2-phenylimino-2:3-dihydro-3:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

Since the 1:4-compound and ω -bromacetophenone do not react to yield the expected thiodiazine (III), the conclusion that 1:4-diphenyl thiosemicarbazide undergoes conversion into the 2:4-variety appears reasonable.

It had however been noticed that 1:4-diphenyl thiosemicarbazide decomposes into phenyl mustard oil and phenylhydrazine

hydrochloride when the thiosemicarbazide is boiled with hydrochloric acid, thus :

Busch (*Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 4596) has, moreover, noticed that alkyl or aryl isothiocyanates combine with salts of substituted hydrazines to yield 2:4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides even at the temperature of a boiling water-bath. The above observations consequently lead us to suppose that in the present case 1:4-diphenyl-thiosemicarbazide slowly splits up into phenyl mustard oil and phenyl hydrazine hydrobromide under the influence of hydrobromic acid liberated by the action of bromacetophenone on a portion of 1:4-diphenyl thiosemicarbazide. The mustard oil and hydrazine hydrobromide then combine to form 2:4-diphenyl thiosemicarbazide which reacts with bromacetophenone in the usual way.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenylimino-2:3-dihydro-3:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

One mol. proportion of 2:4-diphenyl thiosemicarbazide (1.2 g.) and 1 mol. proportion of ω -bromacetophenone (1 g.) were shaken with 10 c.c. of anhydrous alcohol in a flask. Heat was evolved and the thiosemicarbazide passed into solution. The flask was heated for a minute on the water-bath to complete the reaction. The solution was then concentrated and 2 c.c. of pyridine and a little water were added when the base crystallised out. This was collected and washed with dilute alcohol (yield 67 per cent.). The base was dissolved in a mixture of alcohol and pyridine, boiled with animal charcoal, filtered and cooled. The pale yellow needles thus obtained were recrystallised from acetone; m.p. 184°. (Found: N, 12.19; S, 9.18. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires N, 12.24; S, 9.33 per cent.). The base is easily soluble in benzene, chloroform, carbon disulphide and pyridine; moderately so in ether and acetone and sparingly in alcohol.

1:4-Diphenylthiosemicarbazide and ω -Bromacetophenone: Formation of 2-Phenylimino-2:3-dihydro-3:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

Molecular proportions of 1:4-diphenyl thiosemicarbazide and bromacetophenone were suspended in anhydrous alcohol in a flask which was tightly corked. The flask was kept aside at the room

temperature. The thiosemicarbazide passed into solution very gradually. The colour of the solution turned green in about two months. In 5 to 6 months the colour changed to reddish brown and a crystalline precipitate appeared. This was collected after a further period of 6 months. The mother-liquor, on concentration, produced a second crop of pale yellow crystals. The two crops were found to be identical. They crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in pale yellow needles, m. p. 184°. The identity of this product with 2-phenylimino-2:3-dihydro-3:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine was established by usual tests, as also by analysis. (Found: N, 12.33. $C_{21}H_{17}N_3S$ requires N, 12.24 per cent.).

If the condensation of the 1:4-compound with the bromoketone is carried out on the water-bath in alcohol or pyridine, a non-crystallisable product is obtained.

2-p-Tolylimino-2:3-dihydro-3:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

2-Phenyl-4-p-tolyl thiosemicarbazide (1.7 g.), bromoacetophenone (1.3 g.) and anhydrous alcohol (12 c.c.) were shaken for some time when the components passed into solution with evolution of heat. The solution was then heated on the water-bath for a minute or two when the hydrobromide of the condensation product separated out (yield 84 per cent.). The hydrobromide was dissolved in alcohol and aqueous ammonia added to precipitate the free base. When crystallised from acetone using animal charcoal as a decoloriser, the thiodiazine formed colourless crystals, m. p. 166°. (Found: N, 11.93. $C_{22}H_{19}N_3S$ requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

2-o-Tolylimino-2:3-dihydro-3:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

The method of preparation is practically the same as for the preceding compound, 2-phenyl-4-o-tolyl thiosemicarbazide being employed in this case. The hydrobromide is however more soluble.

The base separated from acetone in needles, m. p. 131-32°, (Found: N, 11.74. $C_{22}H_{19}N_3S$ requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

It is highly soluble in benzene, chloroform, glacial acetic acid or pyridine, but moderately so in alcohol or acetone.

If the reaction is carried out in pyridine, the above condensation product is not obtained and the semicarbazide is simply transformed into the isomeric 1-phenyl-4-o-tolyl thiosemicarbazide.

2-Phenyl-4-m-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide.

Phenyl hydrazine (1.1 g.) dissolved in 30 c.c. of alcohol and a few drops of glacial acetic acid was cooled in ice. *m*-Tolyl mustard oil (1.6 g.) also dissolved in a little alcohol was added drop by drop with constant shaking. Colourless crystals appeared after a short time. These were freed from the mother-liquor, washed with 20 per cent. alcohol and finally with ether and dried at the ordinary temperature; m. p. 123°. (Found: S, 12.56. C₁₄, H₁₆, N₃, S requires S, 12.46 per cent.). In presence of warm solvents it is converted into the 1:4-variety, m. p. 173°.

2-m-Tolylimino-2:3-dihydro-3:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

2-Phenyl-4-*m*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide (1.7 g.) and ω -bromacetophenone (1.3 g.) were shaken with 15 c.c. of glacial acetic acid. Heat was evolved and the components went into solution. The solution was heated on the water-bath for a while, cooled and diluted with water when a semi-solid mass was obtained. This was washed several times with water and finally with 40 per cent. alcohol. The crystalline residue was recrystallised from alcohol after usual treatment with animal charcoal when colourless needles, m. p. 119-20° were obtained. (Found: N, 11.82; S, 8.54. C₁₈, H₁₆, N₃, S requires N, 11.76; S, 8.96 per cent.).

The substance dissolves easily in pyridine, chloroform, benzene, or acetone but moderately in alcohol.

The condensation does not take place in pyridine: a conversion of 2:4- into the 1:4-compound takes place.

2-Phenylimino-2:3-dihydro-3-p-tolyl-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

On shaking 2-*p*-tolyl-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide (1.3 g.) and of ω -bromacetophenone (1 g.) in pyridine a clear solution was obtained and heat developed. The reaction was completed on the water-bath and water added when the base crystallised out. It was recrystallised from dilute pyridine, after treatment with animal charcoal, as colourless, rectangular plates, m. p. 122-23°. (Found: N, 12.06. C₂₀, H₁₆, N₃, S requires N, 11.76 per cent.). It is highly soluble in benzene and carbon disulphide, moderately so in acetone and pyridine but sparingly soluble in alcohol.

2-m-Tolylimino-2:3-dihydro-3-p-tolyl-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

The condensation product (yield 89 per cent.) was obtained in a similar manner from 2-*p*-tolyl-4-*o*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide and bromacetophenone. For purification an alcoholic solution of the base was boiled with animal charcoal, filtered and cooled when it separated in colourless needles, *m. p.* 112°. (Found: N, 11·39. C₂₂, H₂₁, N₂, S requires N, 11·32 per cent.). The compound is easily soluble in carbon disulphide and benzene, but moderately so in alcohol, acetone or pyridine.

2-p-Tolylimino-2:3-dihydro-3-p-tolyl-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

2-*p*-tolylimino-2:3-dihydro-3-*p*-tolyl-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine, obtained as above from 2:4-di-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide and *o*-bromacetophenone in an yield of 84 per cent., formed colourless crystals, *m. p.* 145-46°. (Found: N, 11·31. C₂₂, H₂₁, N₂, S requires N, 11·32 per cent.). It is moderately soluble in benzene, glacial acetic acid, alcohol or pyridine.

2-p-Tolyl-4-o-anisyl thiosemicarbazide.

The thiosemicarbazide was obtained from *p*-tolyl hydrazine and *o*-anisyl mustard oil by a process similar to that employed for 2-phenyl-4-*m*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide. It crystallised from benzene in colourless crystals on the addition of ligroin. (Found: S, 11·54. C₁₈, H₁₇, N₂, S requires S, 11·4 per cent.).

2-o-Anisylimino-2:3-dihydro-3-p-tolyl-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

2-*p*-Tolyl-4-*o*-anisyl thiosemicarbazide (1·4 g.) and *o*-bromacetophenone (1 g) were heated with about 10 c.c. of alcohol on the water-bath for five minutes. On cooling, the hydrobromide of the condensation product crystallised out. This was dissolved in dilute alcohol and treated with aqueous ammonia when the base was precipitated (yield 94 per cent.). On recrystallisation from alcohol it formed colourless needles melting at 109°. (Found: N, 11·08. C₂₂, H₂₁, N₂, SO requires N, 10·85 per cent.). The thiodiazine is highly soluble in pyridine or acetone, moderately in glacial acetic acid and alcohol and insoluble in ether. The above condensation could also be effected in pyridine solution.

2-p-Tolyl-4-m-tolyl thiosemicarbazide.

The thiosemicarbazide was obtained from *p*-tolyl hydrazine and *m*-tolyl mustard oil in cold alcoholic solution. The colourless crystals were freed from the mother-liquor by washing with 20 per cent. alcohol and finally with ether. It was dried in air, m. p. 151°. (Found : S, 12.24. C₁₄, H₁₇, N₃, S requires N, 11.80 per cent.). It passes into the 1 : 4-variety (m. p. 167°) when heated with any solvent.

2-m-Tolylimino-2:3-dihydro-3-p-tolyl-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

2-*p*-Tolyl-4-*m*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide (1.4 g.) and ω -bromacetophenone (1 g.) were shaken with 15 c.c. of glacial acetic acid for about 30 minutes when the substances passed into solution with slight rise of temperature. The condensation product when recrystallised from a mixture of alcohol and pyridine using animal charcoal formed prisms melting at 106-107°. (Found: N, 11.39. C₂₃H₂₁N₃ requires N, 11.32 per cent.). It dissolves easily in benzene, chloroform or acetone, moderately so in pyridine or glacial acetic acid and sparingly so in alcohol. Condensation, however, did not take place in pyridine solution.

2-Phenylimino-2:3-dihydro-3-m-tolyl-5-phenyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

A mixture of 2-*m*-tolyl-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide (1.2 g) and bromacetophenone (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid at ordinary temperature and allowed to stand for 3 hours. It was then heated on the water-bath for ten minutes and diluted with much water. The product was purified as before. From a mixture of alcohol and pyridine it was obtained as colourless prisms melting at 158° (yield 60 per cent.). (Found : N, 11.56. C₂₂, H₁₆, N₃, S requires N, 11.76 per cent.).

It is easily soluble in benzene, carbon disulphide and pyridine, but sparingly so in alcohol.

As 2-*m*-tolyl-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide is unstable, the yield of the thiodiazine is very much diminished if the solution is heated just after the addition of the reactants.

2-Phenylimino-2:3-dihydro-3-phenyl-5-p-tolyl-1:3:4-thiodiazine.

The procedure is practically the same as adopted for the preparation of 2-phenylimino-2:3-dihydro-3:5-diphenyl-1:3:4-

thiodiazine, with the difference that *p*-methyl- ω -bromacetophenone was used in this case. From acetone the base separated in yellow prisms melting at 165°. (Found : N, 11.82. C₂₂, H₁₉, N₃, S requires N, 11.76 per cent.)

It is easily soluble in benzene, carbon disulphide, glacial acetic acid and pyridine but moderately so in acetone and sparingly in alcohol.

2-Phenylimino-2 : 3-dihydro-3-m-tolyl-5-p-tolyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine.

2-*m*-Tolyl-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide (1.2 g.) and *p*-methyl- ω -bromacetophenone (1.1 g.) were dissolved in anhydrous alcohol without application of heat. The solution was kept overnight at the room temperature and finally heated on the water-bath for a short time and allowed to cool. Dilute pyridine was added when the free base crystallised out. From alcohol the thiodiazine was obtained in colourless crystals melting at 130°. (Found : N, 11.32. C₂₂, H₂₁, N₃, S requires N, 11.32 per cent.)

It is highly soluble in benzene, chloroform, acetone, pyridine but moderately so in alcohol.

2-p-Tolylimino-2 : 3-dihydro-3-phenyl-5-p-tolyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine.

The condensation was carried out as usual with 2-phenyl-4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide and *p*-methyl- ω -bromacetophenone. The base was liberated using pyridine and was crystallised from acetone in yellow needles, m. p. 180°. (Found : N, 11.43. C₂₂, H₂₁, N₃, S requires N, 11.32 per cent.). The thiodiazine readily dissolves in benzene, carbon disulphide, ether, pyridine, moderately in acetone and sparingly in alcohol.

2-Phenylimino-2 : 3-dihydro-3-phenyl-5-methyl-1 : 3 : 4-thiodiazine.

2:4-Diphenyl thiosemicarbazide (2.4 g.) and monochloroacetone (1 g.) were heated with 15 c.c. of anhydrous alcohol for about 15 minutes on the water-bath. The solution was concentrated and dilute pyridine added to isolate the free base (yield 65 per cent.). It crystallised from alcohol in colourless shining plates melting at 153-54° (Found : C, 68.34 ; H, 5.65. C₁₈, H₁₅, N₃, S requires C, 68.32 ; H, 5.33 per cent.).

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